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CONNECTING PRACTICAL PARTS OF VISUAL ARTS LESSONS WITH MUSIC TO ENHANCE CREATIVITY

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Annotation: Ideas are presented on how to organize visual arts lessons and inspire students by linking them with music and playing pleasant music during the lesson.

Keywords: visual arts, artist, music, dynamic movement, musical-artistic images, artistic expression, tone.

Music and visual arts are deeply interconnected. A talented composer or musician, like a painter, demonstrates a certain symbolic sequence reflecting the energy of their work. Like painting, music also has its unique characteristics. Different types of visual arts create the sense of objective qualities of real existence — volume, color, space, as well as the material form and environment of the subject, movement, and changes. This ranges from emotional accuracy in depiction to illusionism.

Visual arts do not only depict visible objects but also express the temporary development of events, free narration, dynamic movements, and expand opportunities for conceptual understanding of the world. Visual arts reveal the spiritual image of a person, their interactions with others, and the psychological and emotional content of the depicted state. Sometimes, it even creates images that do not exist but are products of the artist's imagination.

As a school subject, visual arts provide elements, knowledge, and skills related to artistic and aesthetic culture necessary for every individual. Regardless of the future

profession of each student, they should enjoy beauty, relax, and restore their energy spent during work. Human feelings, emotions, moods, and worldview are expressed through art.

The Representativeness of Visual Art Images Allows the Artist to Express Their Attitude Toward a Certain Life Event at a High Level; Therefore, It Plays an Important Role in Social Life as an Active Form of Understanding Life and in the Formation of the Mass Consciousness of a Certain System.

It shapes social consciousness as one of the forms of understanding the world and also holds great importance as a form of expressing the hopes and aspirations of the people.

The remarkable power of music to influence the human mind and emotions is connected to its inherently processual nature, which harmonizes with mental processes. The content of musical works is formed through the relationships between musical images (such as comparison, conflict, development). According to the characteristics of this process, the content of music can have various narrative, dramatic, and lyrical features. Among these, lyrical music, which tends to express the inner world and mental states of a person, is much closer to the "inner" nature of music.

The content of music consists of the unity of personal, national, and universal artistic values, in which the spiritual freshness, pace, social thoughts, and feelings specific to a certain nation, society, and historical period are expressed in a generalized form. Musical forms meet the spiritual and educational demands of each era, while simultaneously being interconnected with many aspects of human activity (specific communal events, ethical and aesthetic interactions among people, communication processes).

Music plays a particularly important role as a means of shaping a person's moral and aesthetic taste, developing emotional feelings, and encouraging creative abilities.

Based on these ideas, playing calm music during the practical parts of visual arts lessons, i.e., while students are drawing, stimulates their creative mood and inspiration.

This also helps the teacher to create a peaceful atmosphere and to focus students' attention during the lesson.

In conclusion, organizing visual arts lessons by practically connecting them with music helps to focus students' attention and reduces noise. Integrating music into visual arts lessons has several beneficial aspects. First of all, it stimulates students' creative thinking. Music, in turn, inspires the creation of visual art works. Additionally, listening to music enhances the perception of colors and shapes, makes the lesson process more interesting, and attracts students' attention. The rhythm and tones of music also assist in editing and comparing, while simultaneously providing an opportunity to study the connection between visual arts and music. This increases the effectiveness of the lessons.

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